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IEA Wind TCP Task 52

Review of Mini-Symposium at WESC 2025

MS#01.8: Lidars In and Out of Simulations

A collaboration between IEA Tasks 52 and 57

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[WESC 2025 Mini-Symposium MS#01.8 "Lidars In and Out of Simulations – a collaboration between IEA Tasks 52 and 57"](#)

IEA Task 52 – General Meeting 2025 - Review of Mini Symposium

Agenda

The mini-symposium (co-chaired by Stefano Letizia and Julia Gottschall) was held on 25 June 2025, and comprised the following individual presentations:

- "Sensitivity of the turbulence measurements from ground-based lidars to the beam orientation" by Abdul H. **Syed** (a)
- "A Comprehensive Sensitivity Analysis of Wind Lidar Uncertainty Using a Fiber Optic Bench and Monte Carlo Simulation" by Andrew **Black** (b)
- "LARGE-EDDY-SIMULATION-BASED PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF FLOATING LIDARS - MOTION CORRECTION & WIND PROPERTIES RECONSTRUCTION" by Benjamin **Bouvier** (c)
- "Wind Field Reconstruction Using Single Doppler Lidar: A Lagrangian Approach" by Ignace **Ransquin** (d)

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Task 52 Context

Task 52 mission: make wind lidar the preferred wind measurement tool across applications; we work along four themes:

- (1) universal inflow characterization,
- (2) replacing met masts
- (3) connecting wind lidar, and
- (4) accelerating offshore deployment—while **Task 57** advances model development and validation. This session sat exactly at that interface.

[WESC 2025 Mini-Symposium MS#01.8 "Lidars In and Out of Simulations – a collaboration between IEA Tasks 52 and 57"](#)

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“Sensitivity of the turbulence measurements from ground-based lidars to the beam orientation” by Abdul H. Syed

— Problem & Method

Methods

$$v_r(\theta) = u \cos \theta \sin \phi + v \sin \theta \sin \phi + w \cos \phi.$$

$$\begin{aligned} \langle v_r'^2 \rangle = & \langle u'^2 \rangle \sin^2 \phi \cos^2 \theta + \langle v'^2 \rangle \sin^2 \phi \sin^2 \theta + \langle w'^2 \rangle \cos^2 \phi \\ & + 2 \langle u'v' \rangle \sin^2 \phi \sin \theta \cos \theta + 2 \langle u'w' \rangle \sin \phi \cos \phi \cos \theta \\ & + 2 \langle v'w' \rangle \sin \phi \cos \phi \sin \theta, \end{aligned}$$

Motivation:

Lidar turbulence measurements are affected by **systematic errors** (e.g., probe volume averaging, scanning geometry) and **random errors** (e.g., atmospheric stability, beam orientation)

Key question:

How much does beam orientation impact lidar turbulence measurements?

1. VAD method

- Estimation of u, v, w wind components
- Six equations, three unknowns
- **Cons:**
 - Systematic underestimation due to probe volume averaging effects
 - Variance contamination
 - **Beam orientation matters (?)**

2. Six Beam method

- Directly estimate u, v, w wind variances through matrix manipulation
- **Cons:**
 - Systematic underestimation due to probe volume averaging effects
 - **Beam orientation matters (?)**

Technical University of Denmark

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“Sensitivity of the turbulence measurements from ground-based lidars to the beam orientation” by Abdul H. Syed

— Result/Conclusion

1. Wind direction sensitivity
2. Half-opening angle sensitivity
3. Error metrics
4. Conclusions

Watch out for...

	VAD method	Six Beam method
Systematic errors	From probe volume averaging & From half-opening angle sensitivity	From probe volume averaging
Random errors	From half-opening angle sensitivity	From azimuth-wind direction offset of beams & From half-opening angle sensitivity
Dispersion around mean	Less as compared to the Six Beam method. Usually from half-opening angle sensitivity	From azimuth-wind direction offset of beams & From half-opening angle sensitivity

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"A Comprehensive Sensitivity Analysis of Wind Lidar Uncertainty Using a Fiber Optic Bench and Monte Carlo Simulation" by Andrew Black

— Problem & Method

Diagram of SAFO-MV Calibration Bench

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"A Comprehensive Sensitivity Analysis of Wind Lidar Uncertainty Using a Fiber Optic Bench and Monte Carlo Simulation" by Andrew **Black**

— Result/Conclusion

Conclusions and Next Steps..

- Conclusions:
 - A new, SI-traceable calibration and classification technique for pulsed lidar using fiber optics and Monte Carlo simulation has been developed and tested on 6 systems
 - Calibration time (3 days) reduces the time for lidar calibration by 90% (IEC is ~4 weeks)
 - Derived uncertainties (0.34% @ 8 m/s) are 74% lower than IEC method (1.31% @ 8m/s)
 - The derived uncertainties are within bounds suggested by alternative methods
 - Capable of deriving diverse sensitivities – field Classification no longer needed
- Next steps:
 - Continue to verify repeatability and reproducibility with new systems
 - Collaborate with ISO17025 and national metrology laboratories to refine methodology
 - Experiment with alternative turbulence box configurations and styles (Mann model and LES)

Thank you! Contact me at andrew.hastingsblack@vaisala.com

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"LARGE-EDDY-SIMULATION-BASED PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF FLOATING LIDARS - MOTION CORRECTION & WIND PROPERTIES RECONSTRUCTION" by Bouvier (c)

Problem & Method

LES WIND MODEL & LIDAR MODEL

Large-Eddy-Simulation CFD model obtained with open-source, flexible tools

- NREL SOWFA (over OpenFOAM)
- CNRM MESO-NH
- Fill the gap between low level fidelity simulations and experimental data (no reference)
- Atmospheric Boundary Layer in neutral conditions
- Sampling time 0.25 s, length 30 min, grid spacing 6 m

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Realistic lidar measurement modeling:

- Radial wind speed (rws):
 - wind vectors projection
 - range-weighting
 - Noise
- Space-time scanning sequence
- Beam period 0.25 s
- Altitude 150 m

$$rws = \sum_{i=1}^n m_i \langle \vec{u}_{beam}; \vec{w}(x, y, z, t) \rangle + n_i$$

scalar product

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Result/Conclusion

SIMULATION RESULTS

$T_p = 3.5 \text{ s}, H_s = 0.75 \text{ m}$

Motion correction

- Very small TI increase due to motion → positive effect of buoy stability
- ✓ Correction successfully restores TI to motionless values

TI estimation

Comparing estimation algorithms (motion correction applied)

- ✓ Advanced algorithms bring TI estimates closer to reference TIs
- Possible underestimation by WiSE-Lidar → re-tuning for offshore may be necessary

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"Wind Field Reconstruction Using Single Doppler Lidar: A Lagrangian Approach" by Ignace Ransquin (d)

— Problem & Method

Lagrangian Wind Field Reconstruction (LagWFR)

Minimization of the error

- For this initial guess $\mathbf{V}^n = [V_x^n, V_y^n]$, one computes the sum of the error:

$$f_{err}(V_x^n, V_y^n) = \sum_j^{M_{cross}} w_j \left(V_{losj}^{mes} - \frac{V_x^n \cdot \hat{x}_j + V_y^n \cdot \hat{y}_j}{\sqrt{\hat{x}_j^2 + \hat{y}_j^2}} \right)^2$$

- Repeat the operation for other guesses: $\mathbf{V}^n = [V_x^n, V_y^n]$
- Optimal solution:** optimization problem
 - Con's:
 - Computationally more expensive
 - Convergence not guaranteed
 - Pro's:
 - Reconstruction at arbitrary position and time $(x_{ref}, y_{ref}, t_{ref})$
 - More Accurate ???

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"Wind Field Reconstruction Using Single Doppler Lidar: A Lagrangian Approach" by Ignace Ransquin (d)

Result/Conclusion

Take-away

- 1. Re-think your wind field reconstruction approach:**
 - Rather than (always) considering a **spatial homogeneity** of the flow,
 - **use of a Lagrangian assumption** as a background assumption
- 2. Similar accuracy between the Lagrangian approach and the VAD reconstruction, both numerically and experimentally**
- 3. Pro's/Con's:**
 - VAD: fast, for homogeneous "parallel" flows
 - Lagrangian: arbitrary position and time, for vast area
- 4. Future work:**
 - Further comparisons: coherence, spectral analysis, ...
 - More complex situations: wakes, wind changes, 3D, ...
 - Use with multiple lidars, ...

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Overall Conclusions

- "Sensitivity of the turbulence measurements from ground-based lidars to the beam orientation" by Abdul H. **Syed** (a)
 - VAD method: Less scatter, but sensitive to beam opening angles.
 - Six-Beam method: Higher random errors, dependent on azimuth offset.
- "A Comprehensive Sensitivity Analysis of Wind Lidar Uncertainty Using a Fiber Optic Bench and Monte Carlo Simulation" by Andrew **Black** (b)
 - Reduced calibration time by 90% (3 days vs. 4 weeks).
 - Achieved 74% lower uncertainty compared to IEC standards.
- "Large-eddy-simulation-based performance evaluation of floating lidars - motion correction & wind properties reconstruction" by Benjamin **Bouvier** (c)
 - Motion correction effectively restored turbulence intensity (TI) to reference values.
 - Advanced algorithms improved TI estimation accuracy.
- "Wind Field Reconstruction Using Single Doppler Lidar: A Lagrangian Approach" by Ignace **Ransquin** (d)
 - Outperformed VAD in non-homogeneous wind fields.
 - Suitable for complex scenarios (e.g., wakes, 3D flows).

Practical Implications & take-aways?

Enhanced lidar accuracy supports better wind resource assessment and turbine design.

New calibration and reconstruction techniques likely to reduce operational costs and improve reliability.

Future work: Expand testing to diverse environments and integrate multiple lidar systems.